

Segregation on cold tolerance at the seedling stage in F₂ and B₂ populations of 6 indica/japonica crosses.^a Hangzhou, China, 1985-86.

Cross	P ₁ T	P ₂ S	F ₁ T	F ₂ and B ₂ ^b			X ² c F ₂ (15:1) B ₂ (3:1)	P
				Total	T	S		
Zhonghua 8/Erjiufeng	50	38	17	F ₂ 207	191	16	0.5414	0.25-0.50
				B ₂ 36	28	8	0.0370	0.75-0.90
Zhonghua 8/My 82166	24	40	12	F ₂ 181	169	12	0.0033	>0.90
Zhonghua 8/Qinghuaai 6	24	39	25	F ₂ 184	170	14	0.3710	0.50-0.75
				B ₂ 55	40	15	0.0545	0.75-0.90
Zhonghua 8/Conggui 314	50	31	19	F ₂ 198	185	13	0.0013	>0.90
Reimei/Qinghuaai 6	42	39	31	F ₂ 195	187	8	1.1901	0.25-0.50
Reimei/Conggui 314	27	31	29	F ₂ 144	133	11	0.2667	0.50-0.75

^aT = tolerant, S = susceptible. ^bNo segregation into medium type seedlings such as medium tolerant, medium, medium susceptible.

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Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of soil alkalinity on yield of genotypes in Kanpur

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Alkali soils occur more in arid and semiarid areas. Because of high pH values, these soils are deficient in

important plant nutrients.

We screened 10 genotypes (see table) in plots with pH values 9.2 and 9.6. N-P-K was applied at 120-26-25 kg/ha through urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Maximum grain yield was from Pokkali, Nonasail (Sel.), IR46, and IR4563-52-1-1-3-6. Lowest yield was from IR54. Grain yield was severely reduced with increasing pH. □

Effect of soil alkalinity on grain and straw yields. Kanpur, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	pH 9.2	pH 9.6
IR43	2.9	1.8	5.5	3.9
IR46	3.5	2.8	5.6	3.8
IR54	1.8	0.5	4.2	3.2
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	3.7	2.5	4.0	3.9
IR9763-11-2-2-3	2.9	2.8	3.7	3.5
IR14632-2-2-3	2.1	2.0	8.1	7.5
IR19661-131-1-2	2.8	2.2	5.1	3.8
M242	2.5	2.3	4.8	4.0
Nonasail (Sel.)	3.6	3.0	6.5	5.7
Pokkali	3.6	2.8	6.8	4.7
Mean	2.9	2.3	5.4	4.4

Screening rice entries for coastal salinity and tidal swamp conditions

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We screened 115 germplasm and advanced breeding lines for adaptability to coastal salinity and tidal swamp conditions in the coastal area of south 24-Parganas district, West Bengal.

Tidal water was allowed to enter the plots at regular intervals. The Ece of the soil at transplanting of 30-d-old seedlings was 8.4 dS/m; that of groundwater was 29.9 dS/m. On the commencement of rainfall, those values gradually decreased to a 3.0 for soil and 11.0 for groundwater at 38 d after transplanting (DT). Soil Ece values were

Survival, days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicles, and yield of 12 promising entries for coastal salinity and tidal swamp areas. Hooghly, India.

Variety or line	Survival (%)	Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Panicles (no.)	Yield/plant (g)
Silla	19.1	131	90.6	6.0	5.5
Djambaram	18.2	122	100.4	7.4	11.7
BJN4	21.8	129	67.4	12.0	14.3
BJM5	18.2	132	84.2	11.4	10.5
IR37257-41-3-2-3	37.3	111	96.5	9.4	16.6
IR39558-147-1-3	47.3	132	69.2	9.8	6.2
IR40578-13-2-2-3-2-2	28.2	93	73.8	5.0	15.2
IR4595-4-1-13	31.8	122	78.6	6.4	18.5
IR10198-66-2	27.3	108	91.5	9.3	21.7
SR26B	31.8	110	106.2	7.0	16.5
Hamilton	38.2	103	103.2	9.4	19.2
Malta	31.8	103	98.6	5.4	13.3

below 5.0 dS/m and those of groundwater 10 dS/m and below, from 38 to 68 DT, then tended to increase. Highest soil Ece value (15.1 dS/m) was

at 89 DT.

Percentage survival, days to 50% flowering, plant height (cm), panicles/plant, and yield of 12